

METHODOLOGICAL FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL-ORIENTED COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES OF CADETS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7876432>

Abstract. *This article describes approaches to the formation of a competency approach, a system of knowledge, skills and skills.*

Keywords: *competencies, technology, approach, pragmatic competencies.*

Currently, changes are taking place in the structure and content of education in accordance with the approval of the competent approach in the system of higher professional education, and views on how the educational process should be built are assumed. The competent approach implies a practical orientation of education, emphasizes the development of personal qualities of students, is interconnected with the personal-active approach.

Many researchers agreed that the need to reorient from the educational approach to the competent approach is determined by the contradictions between the results of higher education and the labor market situation. For example, A.A. Verbitsky reveals in detail the nature and causes of discrepancies in the work "Активное обучение в высшей школе: контекстный подход". Among them, the main drawback of the traditionally used definition of educational goals is that it has a very general definition that cannot be compared with real results [1]. As a result, it was not possible to determine the components of the teaching content that are suitable for educational and upbringing goals.

It is emphasized in the scientific literature that the definition of training goals in the terms of competences allows training of specialists in the professional and social spheres, searching and finding new knowledge, and applying them in the conditions of regularly changing professional activity [Baydenko 2007; Shemet 2009]. It is manifested in the performance of certain professional functions, directly incorporating the characteristics of the graduate, which forms the target component of the educational system, into his professional activity. [Pedagogika ... 2010].

One of the factors that must be taken into account in the planning of learning outcomes is the "rapid obsolescence of knowledge competences" [Baydenko 2006: 25]. It is a task for a professional working in this or that field to constantly acquire new knowledge, at the same time, from foreign language sources. In these conditions, it is very important to develop the ability of students to acquire knowledge and skills independently.

Based on the construction of the teaching content in the context of the competent approach, the model of the professional is conditioned by the new target instructions. As a generally accepted factor for the construction of the content of education, in the last decades of the last century, when the content of education was considered as a system of knowledge, skills and abilities, modernization is considered as the confirmation of development and improvement of the theoretical rules that arose within the framework of the existing approach. A competent approach, however, differs from an approach focused on the formation of a system of knowledge, skills and abilities.

The terms "competence" and "adequacy" used by the authors should be clarified. According to A.V. Khutorsky, we use the following definitions [Xutorskoy 2005].

Competence is a set of interconnected personality traits that are given in relation to certain subjects and processes.

Competence is considered as a requirement given to the educational preparation of the student necessary for effective productive activity in a specific field..

Adequacy is the acquisition of appropriate competence, including the relationship to it and the subject of activity. Adequacy is a restored quality of the learner's personality (sum of qualities) and minimum work experience in the given field. Thus, adequacy should be understood as a set of personal qualities consisting of the experience of applying a set of competencies.

Competences are considered in the literature as a combination of knowledge, skills, experience, and personal qualities, which together form the basis of an individual's ability to perform practical tasks in various spheres of activity. Competencies include the following interconnected and mutually dependent entities [5]:

- 1) cognitive - application of theory and "hidden" knowledge acquired in experience;
- 2) functional - an individual's ability to do something in the field of work, education, social activity;
- 3) personal - behavioral skills in specific situation, professional values.

Methodological works of recent years emphasize that the goal of teaching a foreign language is not only the formation of communicative competence as the ability to use the language for communication in various situations, but also the development of the individual in general. Methodologically, the formation of a literate person includes educational and developmental aspects as well as an educational component. The goal of education includes self-improvement, the development of the desire to acquire new knowledge, skills, communication experience, cognitive activity experience. The ability to know and take into account the characteristics of the culture of foreign speakers plays a big role in communication.

In a number of works, the idea that the interconnected formation of communicative and professional competencies is necessary and possible is developed. Vocationally oriented foreign language teaching [1] uses the principles of the contextual approach, which provides for the modeling of the signs of future professional activity in educational activities [2].

The author's views on this work indicate that the structure of communicative competence necessary in the professional field includes the following aspects: oral and written cross-cultural communication; perception of communication as values; readiness to perceive and correctly understand foreign culture; knowing and observing traditions, rituals, etiquette; methods of influencing the communicative process; communication experience and readiness in various communicative situations [3], communicative competences are highlighted in a number of works, in particular in the work of I.A. Saturova [3].

The concept of communicative competence given by the experts of the Council of Europe in the document "European foreign language acquisition competences: learning, teaching, assessment" [www.coe.int/langCEFR] means a model that includes general competences (communicative language competences).

In this model, the socio-cultural competence included in the number of general competencies consists of the ability to know the socio-cultural characteristics of the participants

of the dialogue, the ability to connect one's own culture and that of another, to take into account the difference between cultures, and to observe the norms of behavior in a foreign culture.

This paper talks about the formation of professional communicative competence in a foreign language, it is necessary to include professionally important knowledge, skills, personal qualities, and the experience of performing professional tasks, which are formed by the cycle of all subjects.

Communicative language competence is defined as the amount of knowledge and skills that allow a person to perform certain actions through the means of language. Linguistic competence includes lexical, grammatical, semantic, phonological, orthographic and orthoepic competence [www.coe.int/lang-CEFR].

Creating foreign language thoughts in accordance with a clear communication situation, problem solving, the communicative intention.

Pragmatic competences consist of knowing the principles of constructing thoughts. These thoughts come one after the other in a certain order according to interaction schemes (competency of speech construction schemes) [www.coe.int/lang-CEFR].

Sociolinguistic competences mean the ability to choose the appropriate linguistic means, taking into account the status and social roles of the participants of the communication, according to the situation, the competence in a summary form as a complex obtained from linguistic, speech, socio-cultural and compensatory competences [4]. Linguistic competence is an analogue of linguistic competence given by the experts of the Council of Europe, and speech is an analogue of pragmatic competence. Sociocultural competence is considered as a sum of sociolinguistic, sociocultural and social competences.

In general, it can be noted that the goal and content of the development of profession-oriented communicative competences is determined on the basis of a set of personal knowledge (linguistic and professional), skills, qualities that ensure intercultural interaction in the professional field and include the aspects given below:

1. Personal, which ensures effective psychological interaction, successful independent organization and self-improvement in cooperative activities.
2. Motivational, indicating the desire and need to learn and use a foreign language for the purposes of communication and independent education.
3. Linguistic, which refers to the means of language communication.
4. Discursive, which is considered to be the main ability to build logical and connected thoughts according to the communication situation and purpose.
5. Social and cultural, which is considered as the ability and readiness to take into account the uniqueness of the culture of the main peoples in the perception, understanding and acceptance of foreign culture, establishment and application of interpersonal relations.
6. Sociolinguistic, which refers to the ability to follow the norms of communication accepted in the culture of the speakers of a foreign language, take into account cultural characteristics in the selection of speech tools and the interpretation of perceived texts.
7. Professional, defined on the basis of clarifying the professional and general cultural competences formed by the complex of subjects, including the foreign language given in the state educational standards.

The introduction of the aspects indicated in the development of profession-oriented communicative competences implies the identification of the features related to the importance of competences formed during the training process.

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